

Working Statement Method

Martin Dogniez, PhD Candidate

Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences

University of Liège

&

Dr. Lucas Terrana

Natural History Museum and Vivarium of Tournai

Université Libre de Bruxelles

TANGO 2 Expedition

Estimating tipping points in habitability of benthic ecosystems along the northern WAP (Western Antarctic Peninsula)

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This document has been read and approved by the expedition leader of the TANGO project, the skipper of RV Australis and all the participants to the field expedition to Antarctica.

Signatures

Lucas Terrana
Dive Leader

1. Scientific background of TANGO 2

The overarching objective of the TANGO expeditions is to gather samples and data to help building a benchmark to contribute to our understanding of the drivers shaping the response of shallow benthic communities to contrasting glacial regimes in a fast-warming region of the Southern Ocean, the West Antarctic Peninsula (WAP). It is hoped that the collected samples will refine insights in the tipping points that these communities might face. The objectives are tackled by using a multi-faceted approach matched by the complementary competences of the scientific crew and the sampling gear. The main specific objectives of the project are the following: **(WP1)** study individual responses of selected key species to contrasted environmental conditions; **(WP2)** identify species interactions and assess benthic species competition for resources (food, space) along a latitudinal gradient of different ice conditions; **(WP3)** investigate the ecosystem responses in terms of carbon fluxes along this same sea ice conditions latitudinal gradient and finally **(WP4)** upscale our findings to ecosystem level. Concretely, the TANGO team will collect samples and carry out onboard experiments to understand the spatial distribution of biodiversity, the structure of trophic networks, and the energy (carbon) fluxes from the atmosphere to the sea floor.

The TANGO project, funded by BELSPO (Brain-BE 2.0), is composed by a consortium of Belgian institutions with as project leader Ghent University (UGENT). The other institutions within the consortium are the Free University of Brussels (ULB), Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Science OD-Nature (RBINS), and the University of Liège (ULiège). After a first successful mission carried-out in the south of the WAP (TANGO 1, 13th February - 17th March 2023), the TANGO 2 expedition (4th February – 8th-March 2024) will further expand the panel of environmental conditions explored along the the WAP.

2. Purpose of this document

This Working Method Statement (WMS) aims to describe the general procedures for the diving operations planned in the framework of the TANGO research project mentioned above. This description covers the main points of attention required to ensure that the scientific diving activities necessary to achieve the project's specific objectives are carried out efficiently and safely. The WMS includes:

- A description of the scientific tasks and of the associated material to be used;
- A description of the working area with all preliminary information available in terms of geography and bathymetry;
- A description of the dive platform and the equipment available onboard for communication, navigation, safety and diving logistics;
- A presentation of the diving team including their affiliation, their planned mission onboard, their detailed dive experience and their first aid capacities;
- A description of the administrative requirements including insurances and employers' obligations;
- A description of the logistics for the provision of breathing gas, and of the procedures applied to ensure the good quality of this gas;
- A description of the procedures to manage the saturation and the decompression of divers throughout the mission;

- A detailed risk analysis that:
 - A) Describes how a typical dive will be operated during the mission;
 - B) Identifies all foreseen risks associated to the diving operations planned in the area of interest onboard of the diving platform available, with for each of them specific measures to mitigate or eliminate these risks;
 - C) Lists all necessary diving & safety equipment;
 - D) Details the emergency plan covering the immediate rescue of endangered divers, the primary care to apply to an injured diver and the evacuation procedure in case of emergency;

This working method statement ensure the compliance with Article 5 of the Royal Decree of 23 December 2003 on the protection of workers against the risks associated with work in hyperbaric environments. The WMS, including the associated Operational Risk Management (ORM), will be submitted for approval to all scientific and divers employed in the framework of the TANGO consortium, as well as all the project leaders from each involved institution. This document will also be submitted to the skipper of the research vessel that will be used for the expedition, to the Scientific Crew Leader and to the Health & Safety representant of the specific employers of each diver. It is mandatory that non-divers are aware of the WMS and the safety procedures, as they might be involved in the protocols in case of emergency. The WMS will be signed by all the parties mentioned, stipulating that they have taken knowledge of the procedures mentioned in this document and that they fully endorse them.

3. List of scientific tasks foreseen in the water

The tasks to be carried out underwater are in line with the objectives of the TANGO project. For each work package, the different tasks and necessary equipment are listed below (see annex 11.3 for detailed protocols of each task):

- **Tasks for Work Package 1**

- **Underwater photography** of benthic organisms and **collection of voucher specimens** by hand to build a genetic barcode library of organisms present on site, with matching pictures taken in-situ.
Equipment: Olympus TG6 camera with waterproof housing, Bigblue VL4600P light (4600 lumens), one Trident self-closing collection bag.
- **Collection of sea urchins** *Sterechinus neumayeri* and its potential food sources (algae and sediments) for the study of its gut content and microbiome in contrasted environmental conditions.
Equipment: two Trident self-closing collection bag, three 50mL Falcons.

- **Tasks for Work Package 2**

- **Quantitative sampling** of benthic fauna and flora with **underwater transects** (10 m) and **quadrates** (0.16 m²) in every station chosen along the environmental gradient to study the trophic interactions among the communities (stable isotopes analysis, fatty acids analysis and gut content metabarcoding).
Equipment: three Trident self-closing collection bag, one 30m weighted measuring tape OR one weighted PVC quadrat (40cmx40cm), one putty knife, three 50mL Falcons.

- **Deployment of a Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV)** to map the seafloor and the benthic communities (NB: no divers involved unless loss of the machine or entanglement of the umbilical).
Equipment: one BlueRov2 from BlueRobotics, one tether spool (150m), one Panasonic ToughBook, one GoPro 10.
- **Tasks for Work Package 3**
- **Sediment coring** (10 cm diameter) for the incubation of sediments in order to measure the primary productivity of the soft bottom benthic community, the nutrients dynamic and the gas exchanges between the sediment community and the water column.
Equipment: three Perspex cores (10 cm diameter), one core rack, one hauling line for the rack.
- **Sediment coring** (5.6 cm diameter) to collect the soft bottom infauna for stable isotopes analysis and measure environmental variables (sediment grain size, pigments analysis, total organic matter, total organic carbon content and total nitrogen).
Equipment: three Perspex cores (5.6 cm diameter), one core rack, one hauling line for the rack.
- **Retrieval of a sediment trap** deployed to monitor the sedimentation rates and the composition of the Suspended Particulate Organic Matter in every station with a lift-bag.
Equipment: one Hydro-Bios MST6 sediment trap (12kg in air/8kg in the water), three rigid buoys (8kg floatation each), three standard shackles with securing metal thread, one quick-release shackle, one rotating swivel, 40kg iron weight, three nylon ropes (2.1, 2.5 and 2.8 meters-long respectively), 50kg lift bag (see Annex 1 for a detailed sketch of the installation).

4. Working area

After the first TANGO 1 mission in the Grandidier Channel (Blaiklock Island) and the Bigourdan Fjord (Blaiklock island), the TANGO 2 expedition will focus on the Gerlache Strait (Fig. 1), an area which has already been explored by the same consortium during the Belgica-121 expedition (2019, RECTO-vERSO projects). Based on this first experience, four potential locations were selected for TANGO2: Melchior Islands, Lemaire Island, Hovgaard Islands and Foyen Harbour. For the three first locations, a fine-scale bathymetry map is already available (see Figs. 2–5), based on previous trips undertaken by the RV Australis, the chosen boat for the TANGO expeditions (see below). This is a significant advantage for scientific diving, as the dive sites and their potential specific hazards are identified before the expedition takes place. In each location, dives will be performed on suitable areas for the sampling of soft-bottom communities, and rocky slopes with macroalgae forests, two main habitats of interest for WP2 and WP3. In addition, these sites allow a safe anchorage for the RV, sheltered from dominant winds and where bottom current are inexistent or moderate enough for safe work of the divers (current less than 1 knot). Precise coordinates are not needed for diving, as scientists are looking for habitats rather than exact locations, and the point of immersion may change according to local conditions (for instance in the case of presence of brash ice). Finally, if a site is selected at close proximity to an active ice-front, attention should be paid to the amount of brash-ice and icebergs present *in situ*, so that divers can make surface at any time in case of emergency without risking a collision with floating objects. A summary of the checklist for the choice of the dive site is presented in Table 1. This checklist is also integrated into the diving register with the log sheet of the day.

Figure 1. Map of the WAP with the sampling areas for the TANGO 2023 expedition (orange) and the joint area for the Belgica-121 and TANGO 2024 expedition (red & green); stations visited during the Belgica-121 expedition and planned for the TANGO 2024 are respectively circled in red and green.

Figure 2. Bathymetric map of the planned sampling area for TANGO 2024 in the inner basin of Melchior Islands, with deeper areas in dark blue and shallower area in light blue/white, land and sea areas not surveyed with the echosounder appearing in grey.

Figure 3. Bathymetric map of the planned sampling area for TANGO 2024 in the inner basin of Hovgaard Island, with deeper areas in dark blue and shallower area in light blue/white, land and sea areas not surveyed with the echosounder appearing in grey.

Figure 4. Bathymetric map of the planned sampling area for TANGO 2024 in Lemaire Island, with deeper areas in dark blue and shallower area in light blue, land in orange and sea areas not surveyed with the echosounder appearing in white.

Figure 5. Bathymetric map of the planned sampling area for TANGO 2024 in Foyen Harbor. Whitish areas are the shallowest.

CATEGORY	CRITERIA	REQUIRED FEATURE	CHECK
Sampling location	Depth	≤ 30m	
	Habitat	Macroalgae, soft-bottom	
	Anchorage	Sheltered from the dominant winds and hold the vessel several days in a row	
Environnemental conditions	Wind	< 5 Beaufort	
	Waves	H _s < 1m	
	Current	< 1 knot	
	Outside visibility (fog/snow)	RIBs always visible from the RV Australis, min. 100m	
	Leopard seal	No visual contact before & during operations	
Ice conditions	Type of ice	No fast ice, brash ice inexistant to moderate and slow	
	Icebergs	Clearance of 20m	
	Ice cliffs	Clearance of 100 m	

Table 1. Checklist for the choice of the dive site to complete before deciding to gear-up for diving.

5. Available diving platform

The Research Vessel AUSTRALIS (RV Australis) is a 23m steel hulled, fully rigged motor sailor registered as a commercial – Category 0 (zero – Unrestricted) vessel for cargo and passengers. It carries a comprehensive range of safety, operational and navigational equipment. It sails very well and has a powerful engine (180hp Gardner diesel engine) to push it along at 8+ knots when needed. The general layout of the boat, with space to accommodate up to 10 scientists and 3 crew members, is shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. All diving equipment (with the exception of diving tanks) is stored protected from the elements in the cargo hatch when not diving (on anchor) or while cruising, a hatch which also serves as changing room before/after the dives. The main compressor is also stored in this “dry area”, with a tube which is placed outside as an air inlet while filling (see section 7 for more details). The diving tanks will be stored on deck (“wet area”, see Fig. 7) into a custom-made open cage and they will be firmly attached during cruising and in between diving operations. The divers will be able to get ready both on deck (final assembly of the diving gear) and in the dry area (suiting-up and undressing). All the diving gears will be initially left drying on deck (after rinsing with fresh water whenever enough fresh water is available onboard) and then stored in the dry area during the night/cruising to avoid freezing or splashing.

Figure 6. General layout of the cabins of R/V Australis. Specific spaces are allocated to scientific tasks and diving gear.

Figure 7. Deck layout – deploy and working areas of R/V Australis.

Additionally, the RV Australis carries two zodiac tenders (Bombard Commando C3 (3,8m) & C4 (4,3m) – 15hp Yamaha) which are used for scouting the anchoring areas, deploying instruments, bringing scientists on land for intertidal work and deploying divers away from the main anchoring point. These RIBs (Rigid-Inflatable Boats) can accommodate up to three divers with their diving and sampling gear, with additional space left for a tender and a zodiac driver. These zodiacs are also used as a deployment platform for divers when diving directly from the RV Australis. Indeed, the mooring of the RIB directly to the side of the ship as a “stepping stone” prevents scientists from jumping/climbing directly from the high free-board of the RV Australis, and allows the tender to position as close to the water as possible, allowing efficient help to the divers before immersion and after surfacing. Moreover, with the RIB already in the water and thanks to its mobility, it can immediately be deployed in case of emergency surfacing away from the boat.

Navigation and communication instruments are available onboard:

- Navigation:
 - Radar – Furuno, commercial grade;
 - Side scan sonar and depth sounder (DualBeam & SingleBeam Eco sounder) – Furuno, commercial grade;
 - GPS – Furuno GP32;
 - NOAA satellite live weather imagery receiving capability world cover;

- ENVISAT satellite real time ice extent imagery;
- Auto pilot – TMQ.
- Communication
 - 406MHz EPIRB – CAT1 ACR Global Fix iPro - Beacon ID (Unique Identifier Number) 2DCC7 B1966 FFBFF;
 - SART (search and rescue transponder) IMO authorised ACR with GMDSS (Global Maritime Distress and Safety System) capabilities;
 - Radios with GMDSS capabilities– HF (long distance) and marine VHF with AIS receptor;
 - 6 x VHF marine portable radios;
 - Iridium OpenPort internet – via WiFi on any device – individual email addresses available;
 - Iridium OpenPort separate guest phone;
 - Iridium satellite phone;
 - Starlink Maritime internet - via WiFi on any device – high-speed internet (>100MB/s) for all guests onboard.
 - Independent Garmin InReach system - location, emergency contact, SMS through satellite (Iridium)

6. Scientific diving team

All divers involved in the TANGO 2024 expedition (see the list below) have been trained according to the standards from the host country of their research institution. Besides their diving skills, all the divers are able to contribute to the different scientific manipulations required by the different objectives of the WPs from the TANGO project. All divers have a strong experience of cold-water diving either in Antarctica during TANGO 2023 and/or Patagonia during the MAGELLAN 2023 campaign, or during regular recreational diving in winter in quarries or at sea. The Dive-Leader has a strong background of scientific diving and management of diving in remote places with more than 13 international expeditions. The divers already have previous experience of working together as a team, and additional training sessions will be organized in the months before departure. They will be organized to refresh the deployment of quadrates & transects, as well as the collection of organisms and handling of sampling bags. Basic skills will be rehearsed such as controlled ascend with SMB from depth, air donation to the buddy, or mask exchange underwater with dry gloves. Finally, some tethered dives will be organized in Belgium to refresh the competences learnt during the BSD and practiced in Antarctica. All divers will have received proper and specific training according to the working conditions and the work to be performed, as required by Article 14 of the Royal Decree 23/12/2003.

A training session will be organized by the Dive-Leader to standardize the regulator hoses and placement on the tank valves following DIR standards of technical diving. This approach has several advantages, such as having the same configuration between all the divers, reducing uncertainties during briefings or material management; reducing the duration of action in case of regulator freezing, as everybody will have the primary first stage placed the same way, and therefore everybody will directly know which valve has to be closed; the long-hose on the primary regulator may help air-donation in a situation where scientific material is deployed and divers need space, or if it is a tethered-dive with a buddy line; or also the minimization of entanglement of the equipment with lines, tether or scientific gear, as the hose lengths are optimized to the proper size without any “Christmas tree” effect on the diver.

The regular dives organized in Belgium before the expedition will help to build automatisms with scuba gear, and between buddies, and consolidate the trust between team members. It will also allow to check the adequacy of the diving equipment from each diver. If some inadequacies or technical problems are encountered, the person concerned will take care to fix potential problems well in advance from the departure. If no problem is encountered, divers will still go through a thorough servicing and testing of their gear 2 months before the departure, with an emphasis on the absence of leaks in the dry-suit and dry-gloves systems.

Diving team:

1) Dr. Lucas Terrana

Affiliation: Natural History Museum & Vivarium of Tournai / Free University of Brussels

Employer: City of Tournai

Roles: Dive-Leader, Diver and Tender

Dive Experience:

- ~800 dives
- ~250 scientific dives
- First aid & O₂ provider training: 12/2023
- ABSD: 12/2023-12/2028 (training to be provided in December 2023)

2) Martin Dogniez, PhD Student

Affiliation: Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences / University of Liège

Employer: F.R.S-FNRS

Roles: Diver and Tender

Dive experience:

- ~650 dives in total
- 70 scientific dives
- 18 dives in Antarctica
- 17 dives tethered
- > 200 dives with drysuit
- First aid & O₂ provider training: 19/07/2023
- BSD: 09/2021-09/2026

3) Lea Katz, PhD Student

Affiliation: Free University of Brussels

Employer: F.R.S.-FNRS

Roles: Diver, Tender and ROV pilot

Dive experience:

- ~160 dives in total
- 40 scientific dives
- 12 dives in Antarctica
- 12 dives tethered
- ~80 dives with drysuit
- First aid & O₂ provider training: 14/05/2022

- BSD: 09/2022-09/2027

4) Dr. Camille Moreau

Affiliation: Free University of Brussels

Employer: Free University of Brussels

Roles: Diver, Tender

Dive experience:

56 scientific dives, 130 dives in total

- ~250 dives in total
- 56 scientific dives
- 18 dives in Antarctica
- 16 dives tethered
- ~90 dives with drysuit
- First aid & O₂ provider training: 14/05/2022
- BSD: 09/2022-09/2027

5) Anthony Voisin, PhD Student

Affiliation: University of Liège / Université de Bretagne-Occidentale

Employer: Université de Bretagne-Occidentale

Roles: Diver

Dive experience:

- ~60 dives in total
- 24 scientific dives
- 9 dives in Patagonia (6°C water)
- 1 dive tethered
- ~30 dives with drysuit
- First aid & O₂ provider training: 10/11/2022
- CAH1B: 11/2022-11/2027

7. Administrative requirements

All members of the TANGO 2 dive team will be in possession of a mission order signed by their employer's delegate at least one month before the start of the expedition. This mission order will stipulate the date of the mission, the area to be studied and the dive platform from which the dive will be carried out. It will also establish a clear link between the TANGO consortium, the diver and his employer. It will clearly state that the dive team member will be involved in scientific diving activities, and that all insurance arrangements have been made.

More specifically, all divers will be covered by a professional insurance contracted by their employer (FNRS, ULB, UBO or Museum) covering their civil liability (cover ceiling of 5 000 000 €), as well as any injury resulting from their activity onboard the ship and underwater (cover ceiling of at least 1 000 000€) and any cost linked to search & rescue activities in case of emergency in this remote area (cover ceiling of at least 200 000€). In the case of divers employed by the FNRS, all risks not related to diving activities will be covered by AIG insurances, while Allianz will assume the coverage of the diving activities. For divers from the UBO, the MAIF will assume the role of insurer during this expedition. For ULB employees, insurances will be covered by ETHIAS which covers 75.000€ in case of medical assistance and 1.250€ for ambulant care, and

full coverage of repatriation costs in case of serious illness or accident from the place of the accident to the nearest hospital, and, if needed, to Belgium (also in case of illness, accident or death of an insured's relative in Belgium). These costs include every way of travelling under medical advice (by air, boat, train or road).

Proof on insurance and complete insurance terms will be made available to the Scientific Dive Leader and the Scientific Crew Leader at least two months prior to departure, in order to negotiate modifications in the insurance policies should a weakness in the cover (civil liability, medical expenses or S&R operations) be identified.

In complement of the general medical examination directed by a physician for the participation to the expedition, all divers will have to be in possession of a medical certificate not older than one year before the last day of the expedition, stating that the diver has been deemed fit for diving in accordance with Article 15 of the Royal Decree 23/12/2003 (Belgian divers) or following Articles 33 & 35 of Decree No. 90-277 of 28 March 1990 on the protection of workers in hyperbaric environments and Article R4461-12, 1st Chapter, Title VI, Book IV, 4th Part of the Working Code created by Decree No 2011-45 on the protection of workers in hyperbaric environments (French divers).

Finally, scientific team leader, Prof. B. Danis, and the head of logistics, Mr H. Robert, will follow the procedures required to obtain well in advance the necessary authorisation from the AFSCA for the import of the samples collected, as well as the authorisation from the Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment DG5/Unit for Strategic & Multilateral Affairs for the organisation of this expedition in accordance with the rules of the Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty.

8. Gas availability, quality & planning

During this expedition, divers will have access to six 230 bars 15L steel tanks with double exits. These tanks will be supplied in air with a primary compressor (Bauer – Poseidon PE100-TW dive compressor (100 l/min, up to 330 bar), with an additional one being operational in case of failure from the primary compressor (Cultri-sub MCH-6 dive compressor (100 l/min, up to 330 bar¹). Before the expedition, both compressors will have undergone servicing, insuring that the air they provide respects the limits enacted by the EN-12021 norm. When refilling the tanks, the air intake hose will be placed two meters above the deck of the ship, with the opening oriented in opposition to the origin of the wind, and the compressor will only be operated when no snow or rain is falling, in order to avoid any excessive intake of moisture by the compressor. Similarly, engines of the RV Australis will always be shut down during refilling of the tanks, to avoid any contamination of the air intake. The dive leader will be accompanied by another person to be in charge of refilling the tanks. They will record the usage of the compressor, in order to insure proper servicing in due time.

Throughout the refilling process, and for every tank, moisture & oil will be purged from the compressor every 10 minutes to avoid build-up. Moreover, tanks will be filled with an additional external personal filter equipped with a combination of active coal and molecular sieve (Undersea™ personal filter), in order to reduce any further contamination of the tanks, and to lower the amount of residual moisture that can get into the tank and promote regulator freezing. Finally, throughout the entire diving operations, random tests (Kitagawa™ analysis & control kit) of two dive cylinders will be performed every three days to ensure the continuous

¹ If needed, this compressor will need to be operated on deck, as it is petrol-driven.

good quality of the air supplied by the compressor. Should any potentially hazardous compound see its level rise above the values specified by the EU 12021 norm, the terminal cartridge of the compressor (TRIPLEX-cartridge 057679) will be swapped with a spare one to restore the gas quality. In any case, a new cartridge will be used at the beginning of the expedition. This cartridge will also be changed if the maximum operating time specified by the manufacturer for a cartridge is reached, even though the air testing doesn't reveal any contamination. Then, if the following quality checks guarantee acceptable levels of carbon monoxide and dioxide, oil vapor and water vapor after swapping of cartridge, diving operations with the compressor will resume. If the contaminant levels are still too high, the backup compressor will be put to use after testing the quality of its output gas. As for the primary compressor, backup terminal cartridges (COLTRI™ MCH6 - SC000340) will be available onboard and used if the maximal number of operating hours specified by the manufacturer is reached, or if the air testing reveals any level of contamination. Despite the advantages in terms of safety, especially in the peculiar diving conditions, no Nitrox will be available onboard. Nobody is qualified as a gas blender to make enriched air nitrox onboard, nor it is possible to travel with enough amounts of oxygen. This possibility should be brought to the attention of the skipper, to evaluate the possibility to provide divers with this additional safety measure during potential future expeditions.

Finally, in case of emergency, the boat is equipped with two B50 oxygen tanks (200 bars) and a complete DAN oxygenotherapy kit with a 5L oxygen tank (200 bars). B50 tanks are equipped with a regulator with adjustable flow (see annex). The DAN tank is equipped with a regulator suited for PIN index connection. Altogether, these can support an injured diver with normobar oxygen at 15L/min for 23h. If a long-distance evacuation is needed, or if more than one diver is experiencing symptoms requiring oxygen administration, a Wenoll™ WS 200 Emergency Oxygen Rebreather unit will be available onboard. This rebreather allows to set the flow at 1L/min. There is no problem with valve compatibility across oxygen therapy kits, as both B50 tanks and DAN tank are equipped with their own regulators. The Wenoll rebreather system has to be plugged on a barbed constant flow outlet, which is universally present in oxygen regulators. Coupled with the oxygen reserves mentioned above, this should allow an optimal treatment of patients for nearly 200 hours.

9. Decompression procedure

As for the TANGO 2023 expedition, the targeted habitats will be sampled at depths ranging between 10 m and 20 m most of the time, never exceeding 30 m, and will never entail any mandatory decompression stop. Planification will be made with both Mares Quad (which uses RRBM decompression algorithm) and Shearwater Perdix set on ZHLC-16C with 85/85 GF, the two types of computers that will be used during the expedition. When doing the planification with the software MultiDeco set with the ZHL-16C algorithm and 85/85 gradient factors, at 20 m depth the maximal bottom time allowing a direct ascent to the surface is 32 min (max. ascent speed is 10 m/min). The RGBM model gives 40 min of bottom time at 21 m. Based on the experience of the Belgica-121 and the TANGO 2023 expeditions, this bottom time is more than sufficient to complete the planned underwater tasks. The only exception to this depth limit will be for the photographic inventory and collection of organisms for barcoding, which will potentially extend up to 30 m. Indeed, at this maximal depth, the ROV deployments from the TANGO 2023 expedition showed important differences in terms of species composition compared to the shallower areas. The aim of the photographic inventory and of the barcoding of organisms will be to inventory and document formally this diversity. Nevertheless, these

deeper dives will also stay within the no-deco limit, which corresponds to a maximum of 12 min bottom time using the same algorithm and GF as above.

To consider the saturation state in case of previous dives for each diver, planification with personal dive computers of each concerned diver will be made prior to the next dive. It will allow to plan bottom time accordingly between divers. They will always follow the most conservative decompression mean present in their buddy team. Moreover, during the dives, all divers will respect a 5 min safety margin between the no-deco limit displayed by their computer and their maximum bottom time, in order to avoid borderline profiles. As no fixed buddy teams will be defined during the expedition, all divers will preferably carry two dive computers (one primary and one backup) in order to always be aware of their personal saturation state if their primary mean of decompression should fail during a dive. If for any reason a diver only wears one dive computer, should it fail underwater, that would not be a problem thanks to the planification made with the computers right before diving: the maximum bottom time allowed is known for both the divers prior to the dive and therefore the diver can rely on his/her buddy to control the bottom time and the ascent. Once back to the surface, the diver should replace the battery (if it was a battery fail and not another unsolvable problem) and rest for 24H to be completely desaturated before diving again. If the dive computer cannot be repaired, planification can be made using either USNAVY 93 table for Belgian divers or MT92 for French divers. In any case, bottom times are compared and the most restrictive is considered.

At the end of every dive, a safety stop of 5' at 5m will be observed to evacuate as much as possible the residual nitrogen present in the body of the divers before getting on the ship, and thus increasing the safety margin. However, this safety stop will be skipped if one of the divers experience any unusual serious thermal discomfort. The strict observance of this safety stop might bring some divers to close to a mild hypothermia state.

10. Operational Risk Management

10.1 General procedures

- Standard procedures for boat trips away from main vessel

All the dive missions are performed in sea water; both the RV Australis and the RIBs serve as platforms for these dives. Boats are only operated by the RV staff and nobody from the scientific and diving team will be in charge of their operation. To minimize the dangers that may arise from traveling in remote areas and cold waters the following procedure concerning boat trips (for diving, sampling, measurements) is proposed and will be implemented together with the vessel crew.

Following the general debriefing of the day with all the scientists onboard, every trip will be previously planned on the day before the activity according to a workplan established during a subsequent general briefing. Therefore, after this general evening briefing, the Scientific Crew Leader Prof. Bruno Danis and the Scientific Dive Leader meet together with the skipper Ben Wallis to validate the planned activities for the next day, hereby estimating the duration of each activity and making sure that the number of activities planned is realistic considering their duration. Upon completion, each activity will be logged on both the TANGO 2

mission (excursions) book and on the R/V Australis daily activity log. A board present in the cockpit will inform all the scientists and crew members of the planning of activities and of the expected time for the occupation of the RIBs.

Communication between the RIB and the RV is insured by a VHF radio only operated by the RV staff. A visual watch will be appointed in agreement with the skipper every day and responsible for communication between the RIB crew and the skipper. Before the start of the trip, the time of return to the main ship is established based on the duration estimation made for each activity during the previous day's meeting between the Scientific Crew Leader, the Scientific Dive Leader and the skipper. The estimated time of return is communicated to the captain/second but only when divers and scientific equipment are ready to be deployed, as gearing up may take more time than expected and/or gear adjustments/problems may be encountered. Moreover, at this moment and upon reaching or leaving the dive site, the communication chain between the RIB's occupant and the visual watch is checked. The beginning and end of each dive (diver enters water, diver surface water) needs to be communicated through the radio and acknowledged by the visual watch. Similarly, any safety-relevant issue has to be signalled as soon as possible to the visual watch. If, without prior notice, the estimated time of return is not kept and no radio contact can be established with the RIB, the crew will organize at short notice a search operation in the area explored. The protocol for this search operation is detailed by the captain to all the crew before the beginning of the expedition. During boat trips, all persons onboard are asked to watch out for drifting ice and communicate any hazard. During trips in unknown areas and until deployment of the divers, the water depth under the boat is controlled either with a handheld echo sounder or using the RIB echo-sounder, especially in locations of unknown bathymetry.

In practical terms, for loading the boat, the equipment needed for any scientific activity is transported by hand from the storage rooms or the deck onto the RIB, which is deployed into the water prior to being loaded with the gear. Smaller parts of the equipment are transported in plastic barrels or boxes, scubas or other heavy equipment are carried individually.

- Standard procedures for diving operations

Before departure from South America, and after the general briefing given by the skipper regarding the safety onboard of the RV Australis, the ORM and especially the emergency plan it contains will be reviewed one last time with the members of the dive team, the Scientific Crew Leader and the skipper. The latter will introduce all divers to the equipment involved in the various scenarios of this emergency plan, and they will check together that this equipment is functional and ready to be deployed.

Dive missions are planned to provide sampling material (flora, fauna, sediments, sediment cores), to provide underwater videos or photos that cannot be taken with the use of the Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV, which will be part of the cruise special equipment, see further) and for search and recovery tasks as well as for safety reasons (in case of emergency due to entanglement) in direct relation to these scientific tasks. In light of the difficulty to have a quick access to a hyperbaric chamber, and because of the increased decompression stress imposed by the cold water in the working area, the dives will all be "No Deco" dives. Their planification will be done by following the most conservative mean of decompression used by the divers onboard, assuring that the actual bottom time will be 5 min less than the maximum bottom time for no deco allowed at a specific depth, allowing to pack all the scientific gear in a sufficient amount of time before ascending and not being

border line with the deco profile. The dive plan will be task-related and it will usually follow a square profile (descent, bottom, work done within 5 min from no deco limit, ascent, safety stop if conditions allow it, exiting the water), unless the task will require a multilevel-dive. In this case, it will clearly be explained during the pre-dive general briefing and bottom times at each targeted dive planned accordingly. This means that in this case (and for every dive), operations will always start at the deepest point.

As general matters, because of the limited cruise time and the notorious variable weather conditions often experienced in the Antarctic, the normal working days won't apply (e.g. weekend days won't be considered as days off). The work will be accommodated to allow the completion of the envisioned dive tasks considering the weather and ice conditions. Even though repetitive dives will be allowed and planned, to avoid increasing the risks due to nitrogen accumulation linked with this repetition, there will always be at least 3 hours between immersions, with a maximum of two dives performed per diver and per day (with the exception of emergency interventions or emergency recovery of critical gear lost and, in this case, the next dives will be after an interval of 24 h for the concerned divers). Moreover, as it is standard procedure, an off-gasing day will be observed for each diver after he/she has completed five consecutive days of diving. Additionally, the divers will be required to have good uninterrupted sleep, and to maintain a good level of hydration throughout the whole cruise. Alcohol consumption will be forbidden between repetitive dives, and of course before any dive.

Again, normal working hours are not applicable in light of the limited time of the cruise, and due to the extra diving-related working time needed to rinse and maintain the diving equipment, refill the tanks and prepare the scientific material needed for the tasks. The dive leader will also work extra time to record and document all the diving activities of the day on a pre-printed logbook (the register, with full details on the site, tasks, profiles and divers) and on diver's personal files (each/diver with personal record of their diving activities, which will be countersigned by the Dive Leader of the TANGO 2 expedition, in accordance to Article 9 to 12 of the Royal Decree 23/12/2003).

As required by Article 13 of the Royal Decree 23/12/2003, this activity register will include the following information:

- 1) Identification of the employer;
- 2) The date, duration and location of the work;
- 3) The nature of the work and the work equipment to be used;
- 4) The name and function of all workers involved on site during the work;
- 5) The composition of breathing gases;
- 6) Pressure at time of exposure;
- 7) The address of the hospital or institution where emergency care can be administered;
- 8) Any accident or incident that occurred during the work;
- 9) The address of the decompression chamber.

As mentioned before, before departure to the WAP the Operational Risk Management will be fully reviewed with all the crew and questions will be answered, if any. Once arrived in the WAP, if the task planning allows, a check dive will be carried out by each diver prior to the beginning of the dive mission in order to verify the correct functioning of the equipment and calibrate the weight to the local salinity. If not, to avoid overloading the divers in this environment, the first scientific dive will be dedicated to one of the least challenging tasks planned (i.e., collection of sea-urchin or documentation of the benthic communities with collection of voucher specimens). Regardless, the training dives organized in Europe prior to departure will allow the divers to be operational almost immediately, and quickly regain the automatisms built up with the other members of the team.

Most of the dive sites are already explored and mapped thanks to the previous expeditions led by the TANGO consortium. If any new site should be explored, features such as tides, current and visibility will be assessed prior to each diving activity by means of ROV deployments, video analysis and echosounder (hull mounted ADCP). When diving in sites close to other bases (e.g., Palmer Station, Melchior Base, Yelcho Base and Vernadsky Station), contact with the responsible of the base will be taken to allow exchange of information and surveillance. The diving tasks will be planned based on weather forecasts making sure that appropriate good weather windows are selected as buffer for potential unforeseen developments of the work (i.e., never dive if bad weather is expected around the expected ending time of the dive itself).

Prior to every dive, during the general briefing the team and the role of each person is established, the evening before the planned dives of the next day. Two divers are chosen considering their saturation state and number of dives, as well as their general state (fatigue, illness, mood, apprehensiveness, ...). A back-up diver is designated, that will held the surface security fully equipped with undersuit, drysuit and the mask, snorkel and fins ready to be put, as well as a tender (if needed), and a responsible of the register onboard the RV who will communicate with the RIB by radio.

Every morning, before the start of the operations of the day, a dive briefing will be held with the whole diving team and the Scientific Crew Leader. During this briefing, the tasks planned during the previous day's briefing are exposed to the divers, and a precise planification is made for each dive envisioned. Safety procedures and dive plans are also reminded. As previously mentioned, no dives will be planned that require compulsory decompression stops and no dives will be planned deeper than 30 m. It is also at this moment that buddy systems are decided, and that the roles of "primary diver" and "assistant(s)" are distributed among the members of the buddy systems. The divers confirm or not that they are in a state to dive. Practically, the main role of the second diver ("assistant") assisting the "primary diver" will be to keep track in real time of the diving parameters (total dive time, time left before for decompression stop, air consumption, ...), and secondarily to help the primary diver to handle the gear and samples, while sometimes contributing to the sampling itself. Generally speaking, the dive leader will make sure to organize the dive team in such a fashion that the dive tasks will be planned accounting for individual skills and physical fitness. This means that if any diver feels that his/her physical or mental capacities are not in line with any of the foreseen tasks, he/she won't be asked to take part in them, and buddy systems will be arranged taking into account these individual preferences/reserves. For every dive, a staff member will have a VHF to communicate with the RV. No solo dives are planned during the expedition.

Depending on the situation (e.g.: presence of current, bad visibility) or on the feeling of the divers (e.g. preference for a direct attachment to the exit point to facilitate the navigation underwater), the team members will have the possibility to be tethered to the RV Australis/RIB to accomplish their tasks, and/or to be attached together with a buddy-line (see Table 2 for the scenarios of tether use). In this situation, thanks to the tethering of the dive leader from the buddy system, communication with the divers will be possible via the tether line by means of pre-agreed pull codes, and the divers will exit the water at their entry point. If diving from a shotline, a strobe might be attached to find the line back after completion of the tasks.

Tethered dives will not be obligatory if environmental conditions are good. When diving untethered from the RIB away from the RV Australis (only when the current and visibility conditions allow it), divers will shoot their SMB directly from the bottom after the completion of their task, and then ascend along the line at no more than 10m/min to reach the depth of their safety stop. This will allow the diver to focus on their task without thinking about finding back the anchorage point. In this case, when divers are underwater, the RIB will never be anchored and always fully mobile in order to assist the divers should they need to surface in an emergency case. A visual watch for leopard seals will also care about the directions of the bubble and follow the divers. Meanwhile, after surfacing of the SMB, the RIB will approach the divers and get into position to retrieve them, taking care to not obstruct their surfacing point. Finally, when diving directly from the RV Australis at the main anchorage, there are two options. Either the RIB is ready to be mobile, in this case the divers can be untethered and surface security is insured by the RIB; or in the other case the RIB is not ready to be deployed (engine problem,...) and thus the divers need to be tethered. In any case, a third diver will be fully equipped with undersuit, drysuit and her/his mask, snorkel and fins ready to be put in order to enter the water if an emergency arises.

Schematically, the dive procedure for every task will be the following:

- 1) The driver (staff member) embarks into the RIB.
- 2) The surface tender (if needed, otherwise the backup diver) and the driver transfer the safety & scientific equipment into the RIB; meanwhile, the divers gear up on the RV Australis.
- 3) The two divers (fully equipped except fins, mask and scientific gear) embark on the RIB, followed by the security diver and by the surface tender who boards last.
- 4) Sailing towards the sampling station (when diving away from the RV Australis); the surface tender keeps track of the depth while the divers and the driver look out for drifting ice.
- 5) When arrived on top of the sampling station, the driver takes the GPS point (when diving away from the RV Australis and if not already done during a previous dive) and maintains the RIB above the location; meanwhile, divers get ready (fins and mask).
- 6) After checking that the way is clear, the tender gives the signal to the divers to enter simultaneously in the water; they regroup at the surface and hold the RIB railing to stay close to it.
- 7) The surface tender proceeds to the attachment of the tether to the leader of the dive (if the dive requires it), followed by the securing of sampling gear to the attachment points of the BCDs from the divers.
- 8) When ready, and after signaling to the tender and driver, the divers go down to their working depth; at this moment, the driver or the tender signals the visual watch on the RV Australis that

the divers have begun their work and the responsible onboard the RV Australis writes the time of immersion. During tethered dives, the tender checks regularly that everything is okay through the agreed pull code; similarly, divers signal the tender their progression through the dive (beginning of the work, ascent to the safety stop and completion of the safety stop).

- 9) Dive ends when the task is completed, when the maximum planned bottom time is reached (maximum 5 min before deco), when a diver reaches 1/3 of its gas supply, when a diver experiences cold, when one of the decompression means fails, when one regulator freezes, when a leopard seal is spotted underwater or when divers are separated. The surface team can also recall the divers in the following cases:
 - An external event requires the emergency exit of divers. Then, the tender recalls the diver with a pre-agreed pull code (tethered dives), or by dumping a Diver Recall Signal in the water; if unsuccessful, the driver recall the diver by continuously revving the engine.
 - The divers are still in the water and they reach the 5 min mark before the no-deco limit planned, and no SMB is visible at the surface (non-tethered dives). Then the tender recalls the diver with a pre-agreed pull code (tethered dives), or the driver recall the diver by revving the engine (sequences of 2 revvs/pause/2 revvs).
- 10) Divers ascend along the tether up to 5m to perform their safety stop (tethered dive), or the leader of the buddy system shoots its SMB before ascending along the line up to 5m to perform the safety stop; if divers experienced unexpected levels of coldness and are incapable of holding the safety stop, it can be skipped.
- 11) For untethered dives away from the RV Australis, the driver positions the RIB close to the SMB.
- 12) After surfacing, divers regroup next to the boat and hold the railing of the RIB to stay at close proximity.
- 13) The surface tender retrieves the samples and the scientific gear first. Then, the divers remove their leads and hand them (with potentially the SMB) to the tender who takes them in the boat. Afterwards, divers remove their tank & BCD at the surface after inflating their drysuit and the BCD. The tanks & BCDs are brought back onto the ship with the combined efforts of the tender and the divers in the water.
- 14) The divers climb back into the RIB with the help of the tender, once all are onboard the driver or the tender signals the visual watch onboard of the RV Australis that the divers are retrieved.
- 15) Once divers are ready and the gear is secured, sailing back to the RV Australis if necessary, same procedure than on the way in.
- 16) Once at the RV Australis, the tender go onboard first and takes the samples first. Then, with the help of divers, the safety and diving gear is brought back onto the main deck.

As a concluding remark, it is clear that, in any situation, the dive leader, the expedition leader and/or the skipper can decide not to allow a diver to enter the water and that without notice if deemed necessary for safety reasons. Similarly, all dives are conducted by free will from the divers, who can abort a dive at any point without notice and explanation.

Type of dive	Surface tether use	Buddy line use
First dive in a new sampling location	Mandatory	Mandatory
Dive from RV Australis with RIB not working (engine issue,...)	Mandatory	Advised
Dive from RV Australis with RIB available	Possible upon demand of the divers (RIB anchored)	Possible upon demand of the divers
Presence of brash-ice	Mandatory	Possible upon demand of the divers
Low-visibility dive	Advised	Advised
Dive in current (< 1 knot)	Advised	Advised
Sediment coring*	Possible upon demand of the divers	Possible upon demand of the divers
Benthic invertebrates quantitative sampling*	Possible upon demand of the divers	No
Photographic inventory*	Possible upon demand of the divers	No

Table 2. Summary of guidelines regarding the use of tethers and buddy line for the various dive conditions and underwater tasks planned.

10.2 Dive Mission Risks analysis

- First category: hazards linked to the usage of high-pressure gas and of diving equipment

Risk n°1:

Use of high-pressure compressor

✓ Control n°1:

Only authorized personnel trained by the skipper of the ship will operate the compressor. The compressor itself fulfils all local relevant legislation and safety control or national legislation of the diving team in case no local legislation exists. The compressor will have been serviced before the beginning of the cruise to check for any potential defect of hazard, and a service report will be made available to the Scientific Dive Leader and the Scientific Crew Leader.

Risk n°2:

Use of high-pressure diving tanks

✓ Control n°2:

All tanks used during this mission follow Belgian legislation, i.e. a pressure test & visual inspection every 5 years and in alternance every 2,5 year a visual inspection. These tests are stamped in the upper side of each

tank². However, as the diving tanks (15L 230bars) were purchased new in Europe during the last trimester of 2022 (manufacturing date: 06/2022), they haven't required yet any of these inspections.

⚠ **Risk n°3:**

Pollution of the breathing gas

✓ **Control n°3:**

Following the Belgian legislation, the quality of the air output from the compressor is regularly checked against EU 12021 norm. Nevertheless, for added safety, the primary and backup compressors will be serviced and checked for air quality prior to the beginning of the cruise and every two days, with a special emphasis on the presence of any excessive residual moisture, in order to minimize the risk of freezing for the regulators. A copy of the service documentation will be given to the Scientific Dive Leader to be added to the final TANGO2 Diving Activities Report. Finally, as stated in section 7, all tanks will be filled with an additional external personal filter to insure the cleanness of the gas.

⚠ **Risk n°4:**

Personal diving equipment loss or damage

✓ **Control n°4:**

Research laboratories and the TANGO project budget holders will arrange with their staff the use of personal diving gears (not purchased through the project). In case of loss or damage to the equipment, the research laboratory insurance will arrange the speedy replacement of the lost item(s) by identical/similar equipment as requested by the diver, and assume the cost of this replacement. If very specific equipment is needed for specific diving tasks, the research laboratory will fund the acquisition.

⚠ **Risk n°5:**

Faulty/malfunctioning equipment (drysuit, regulators, etc...)

✓ **Control n°5:**

All divers will make sure to bringing equipment in perfect conditions, to have regulators and drysuits serviced by competent personnel before the mission starts and test it during test dives before packing it for the cruise. Proof of servicing will have to be provided to the Scientific Dive Leader before the start of the expedition. If any problem appeared, it is the responsibility of every diver to fix it before departure. Moreover, it is advisable that each diver carries with him one spare for every sensitive equipment used (e.g. two sets of masks, one backup computer, spare fin straps). Additionally, for less common type of failures, a spare kit will be put together for the benefit of all the members of the diving team (e.g. spare drysuit inflator/purge, spare swivel for a pressure gauge, neoprene glue and neoprene bands in case of tearing from a neck seal, set of standards o-rings for regulators, ...).

² R YYYY/MM + stamp of the authorized testing company for pressure test and RR YYYY/MM + stamp of the testing company for visual inspection

- Second category: hazards linked to boat and boat operation

⚠ Risk n°6:

Working in a slippery zone

✓ Control n°6:

Drainage on the floor inside the room provides elimination of the water. Wipers will be available and should be used when needed. The deck is coated in non-skid/non-slip painted surface, nevertheless extra caution is requested by all the crew members and proper shoes will be compulsory when working on deck and not equipped for diving. Additionally, when ice settles on the deck overnight, the crewmembers take care to spread salt on the slippery areas before the divers get ready, to make their movements safer. Moreover, divers will be instructed to take special care when moving around or un/loading equipment from/on the RIBs.

⚠ Risk n°7:

Wrong handling of the boat, missing safety equipment, breakdown

✓ Control n°7:

Only competent personnel from the RV Australis crew will handle the RIBs. The safety equipment will be regularly checked (e.g. charging the mobile transceivers prior any RIB trip), as well as other equipment of the boat (e.g. presence and integrity of the anchor & anchor rope with a length adapted to the site, availability of two back-up paddles). All members boarding the RV Australis and the RIBs are required to follow procedure for boat trips, according to the initial briefing given by the skipper prior to the departure from South America.

- Third category: hazards linked to the diving operations

⚠ Risk n°8:

Strong currents that could make the dive difficult or the divers drifting

✓ Control n°8:

Local tide tables can be retrieved for several days in advance from the web and will be used to make sure that dives are planned outside of the strongest ebb/flow periods. However, the operation area has a small average tidal amplitude of 0.5 m, which suggests moderate tidal currents. During the previous expeditions, no extraordinary current features (e.g., underwater rivers) were recorded in the planned dive sites of the TANGO 2024 campaign. Moreover, most diving sites will be along the coastline to be able to sample shallow fauna, and will therefore be located in the sheltered and less exposed to currents part of the Strait. Still, as mentioned in the general dive procedures, the presence of strong currents will be assessed by means of CTD deployments (checking the presence of distinct water masses throughout the water column that could indicate “underwater rivers” with strong currents), ROV deployments (checking the potential drift of the ROV) and video analysis (visually assessing the strength of the current based on the movement of sediments and algae) and echosounder (detecting the presence of nepheloid layers close to a soft bottom that could indicate strong bottom current) upon arrival on a new site. Even if no anomaly is detected, every first dive on a new

location will be tethered and performed by the Scientific Dive Leader supported by the second most experienced diver in the team. Thus, divers will be able to assess directly the diving conditions on site in the safest way possible. Then, only if conditions allow it, untethered dives will be considered. Generally speaking, no dives will be performed with a current speed equivalent to 1 knot or more, as all divers will be equipped with drysuits and carrying sampling gear that will reduce their swimming capabilities and increase their effort.

If weather conditions of the previous days result in strong waves at a given dive site, this site is not visited that day or a new evaluation of the conditions on site is carried out. For this estimation both the safety of the diver as well as the safety of the boat personnel are considered. In the diving area, only very little ship traffic is present; larger cruise ships may be present but mostly in correspondence of research stations or important biodiversity hotspots.

⚠ Risk n°9:

Bad weather conditions such as fog or strong waves that may endanger the personnel during transfer of personnel and gear between the RIB and main vessel, or put divers at risk divers when going in and out of the water

✓ **Control n°9:**

Dives will be cancelled if the presence of fog reduces the visibility in such a way that it impairs the surveillance of the RIB by the appointed visual watch, or if it is dense enough to prevent the tender and/or the visual watch to spot divers in distress at the surface. Similarly, if fog rises during the dive, it will be aborted and the tender or the driver of the RIB will recall the divers (see recall procedures in the “*Standard procedures for diving operations*” section). If weather conditions of the previous days result in strong waves at a given dive site, or if the wind is too strong at a given time, this site is not visited that day or a new evaluation of the conditions on site is carried out. For this estimation both the safety of the diver as well as the safety of the boat personnel are considered. Practically, dives will have to happen with wind speed of < 5 Beaufort and mean waves height ($H\sigma$) lower than 1 m.

⚠ Risk n°10:

Third-party boats traffic (tourism, military or scientific) causing a collision with a diver

✓ **Control n°10:**

In the diving area, only very little ship traffic is present; larger cruise ships may be present but mostly in correspondence of research stations or important biodiversity hotspots, and not in the remote fjords and bays which are planned to be part of the sampling stations from the TANGO 2024 campaign. Regardless, an alpha flag will always be displayed on the mast of the RV Australis when anchored with divers in the water, and on the RIB when assisting diving operations. Moreover, when diving from the RIB (which will always stay in visual range from the main boat), the visual watch appointed onboard of the RV Australis will be especially vigilant to any incoming boat that could interfere with the diving operations, and warn them well in advance through VHF contact from the presence of divers in the area.

⚠ Risk n°11:

Poor visibility in the water due to particles influx linked to summer freshwater runoffs

✓ Control n°11:

Reduced visibility does not generally compromise the work, especially as the members of the dive team will have been trained in confined Belgian waters where poor visibility is commonplace. If extreme cases of bad visibility are likely, for example during sediment coring, divers will be tethered and have a buddy line and pay special attention to stay close during the underwater work. Moreover, all divers will carry a powerful dive light during all dives, and at least one spare lamp will be available by buddy team.

⚠ Risk n°12:

Diving in polluted waters

✓ Control n°12:

The diving area is a completely unsettled area (with the exception of the research stations). Therefore, contaminations are not expected. The only “contamination” may be sediment introduced by melting glaciers but it does not represent a health hazard. Nevertheless, divers will be equipped with drysuits and drygloves, which will drastically reduce any exposure to any potential contaminant in the environment. If after a dive a contact with an unexpected contaminant is suspected (e.g., redness and irritation of the skin), divers will thoroughly rinse their face (only exposed part to the water) as soon as possible, and contact will be made with the physician of the expedition for a teleconsultation.

⚠ Risk n°13:

Decompression sickness

✓ Control n°13:

The risk of decompression sickness is minimized by different manners. The emergency procedures is detailed in p32.

1-Quality of breathed air

As mentioned before, air quality will be check with proper tests for any pollutants, insuring a good-quality air for all divers. Compressor will run when the engines of the RV Australis are off to avoid any gas pollutant.

2-Cold management

All divers will make sure to wear proper undersuits and gloves to delay cold sensation. If it is not tolerable anymore during the dive, it will be aborted **even if scientific tasks are not fulfilled**.

3-Physiological state and post-dive behavior

All divers will make sure to stay correctly hydrated during the whole expedition, have sufficient amount of sleep, and eat well. Drinking alcohol will not be authorized when dives are planned. Smoking will be prohibited during the whole cruise. Additionally, an “off-gasing” day will be observed for every diver after

having performed five consecutive days of diving. Finally, during all the briefing, all leaders will make sure that divers will dive with in mind “Safety first, Work second”, meaning that it is always better to leave a task unfinished than to put yourself at risk.

4-Static Planification

All dives will be rigorously planned based on the most conservative dive computer of the buddy team chosen for the task foreseen, always within the no-deco limits. The dive plan will be carried out in such a way that the tasks will be easily completed within one single dive and without the need to break the no-deco limit.

5-Dynamic Planification

As mentioned above, the presence of an “assistant” diver responsible for the monitoring of the diving parameters throughout the dive should ensure that no limit will be exceeded through carelessness. If during the dive one of the parameters should come close to the agreed threshold fixed during the planification without any reaction of the primary diver, the assisting diver will warn his buddy of the situation. The dive will then be terminated before reaching any fixed limit. Additionally, when allowed by the dive computer, an alarm will be set 5 minutes before the maximum no-decompression bottom time, leaving 2 minutes to the divers to pack their gear and samples before ascending, and still have a 3 minutes safety margin before the absolute maximum no-decompression time. Nevertheless, if divers should enter the decompression zone in spite of these preventive measures, all decompression stops will be followed with an additional safety Stop (5 minutes at 5 meters).

Risk n°14:

Freezing of a regulator

Control n°14:

All the divers will have to use two 2nd stages regulators with separated 1st stages placed on different exits of the bottle. Moreover, the primary 2nd stage regulator will be placed on a separate 1st stage from the drysuit inflator to avoid excessive air demand on one 1st stage and hence likely cause its freezing. These regulators will have to comply with the EN250:2014 norm, stating that they are intended to be used in waters below 10°C. They will have undergone thorough servicing maximum two months before the beginning of the campaign, making sure that their breathing capabilities are still optimal. Moreover, the servicing of the compressors before the campaign will ensure that the amount of residual moisture in the output air is below the limits fixed by the EN 12021 norm, and personal external filters (combined molecular sieve & active coal) will be used to refill every bottle in an attempt to further reduce the moisture content of the air arriving in the tank. Finally, during the training dives organised in Belgium, drills will be organised to teach all the divers to react appropriately to this situation, insuring that there will be no escalation in case this incident should arrive. All divers will have the same hose and stage configuration: in this way, the closing of the valve will be one in the same way for everybody (right tank-take action on the left of the diver’s head when facing him/her).

⚠ Risk n°15:**Out of air situation****✓ Control n°15:**

During all dives, divers will follow the rule of thirds. This means that for a tank with a starting pressure of 210 bars, the half-dive mark will be fixed at 140 bars, and the reserve pressure at 70 bars. Divers will be reminded to always inform their buddy when reaching these key values, and to end the dive upon reaching the air reserve. Moreover, as stated previously, all dives will be performed by two divers, with one having for primary task to monitor in real time the diving parameters throughout the dive. With this method, even if the primary diver gets lost in its underwater tasks, the assisting diver will make sure to keep track of the air consumption of their buddy team. This should prevent any surprise related to an air supply dropping faster than foreseen. Nevertheless, despite these precautions, a short-on-air situation can still happen (e.g., double freezing of the regulators, faulty pressure gauge, complete failure to comply with the no-decompression limit leading to considerable decompression stops, ...). In this case, a spare 15L tank with two regulators will always be available for the divers and deployed from the RIB if the yellow SMB is shot to the surface. During tethered dives, with the RV Australis or the RIB immobile, the safety tank will always be deployed closed under pressure and equipped with two regulators under the boat. If this emergency occurs while diving untethered, with a mobile RIB, divers will shoot their emergency yellow SMB to alert the surface safety that an immediate assistance is needed. In that case, the RIB will position itself close the SMB and drop the safety tank along the line, and the surface tender will prepare himself to help a diver potentially in distress at the surface.

⚠ Risk n°16:**Cooling/hypothermia of the divers****✓ Control n°16:**

The diver changes clothes only inside the heated cargo hatch. The divers are equipped with appropriate dry suits and underwear (multilayers/heating jackets are encouraged). Dry gloves are compulsory part of the equipment, with spare thick neoprene 'wet' gloves and spare rubber gloves for the dry gloves system. Heated gloves are authorized depending on the diver's preferences. The divers will be protected from cooling during the transit to the dive site and on the way back by appropriate protective clothing (e.g. sailing jacket, hardshell). In case of severe hand cooling, an event witnessed during TANGO 2023, hand warmers will be available for the divers as they exit the water, with thick down gloves/mittens. After the dive, warm drinks and light food will be available. Additionally, divers that wish to do so will be encouraged to take a warm shower. However, they will be warned to keep the warmth from the water at a reasonable level to prevent heat shocks, a promoting factor of decompression sickness immediately after a dive. Finally, during the tasks, any diver that would experience discomfort due to cooling will be encouraged to abort the dive.

⚠ Risk n°17:

Diving under brash ice, collision with drifting ice, wave due to collapsing iceberg or ice front

✓ Control n°17:

As none of the divers are formally trained for ice diving or even for dives in an overhead environment, no dives will be performed under ice-sheets. In case of brash-ice diving, all dives will be tethered. When drifting ice is present, the boat should sail at moderate speed and all person aboard will watch for potential collisions. If too much drifting ice is present on the dive site, the dive could be cancelled if the situation is deemed dangerous (e.g., quantity of brash ice preventing the free exit of divers at any time, presence of many large and unstable icebergs, instability of a nearby ice-cliff, ...). Similarly, if the dive already started and that the ice conditions evolve for the worse, the dive could be aborted. On each dive site, a big clearance distance will be observed from any large iceberg (>50 m) or ice-cliff (>100 m).

⚠ Risk n°18:

Entanglement in the line during tethered dives or entanglement of the line in the environment

✓ Control n°18:

All divers will have been trained and have practiced tethered dives before the start of the TANGO 2024 expedition, making sure that they know how to interact with the lifeline and to position themselves in a way that they minimize the risk of entanglement. If despite this training a diver was to be trapped by the tether, without possibility to free himself, his/her buddy will help the entangled diver, either manually or with the help of a cutting tool. If the tether happened to be stuck in an element of the environment, both divers will follow the line until they find the source of the problem. There, if possible, they will have the occasion to try to disentangle the lifeline. If not possible, as the lifeline will be attached to the BCD of the divers with a stainless-steel carabiner, it will always be possible to abandon the tether by detaching this carabiner. As a last resort, just as for a direct entanglement of the diver in the line, divers will be able to cut the line with their tool. In case of abandon of the lifeline, divers will shoot-up an orange SMB and ascend to the surface. If, because of the entanglement, other incidents requiring the immediate assistance of the surface safety have arisen (e.g., air shortage due to stress and exercise and/or unplanned lengthy decompression stops), divers will shoot-up their yellow emergency SMB, and the RIB will come to the assistance of the divers as detailed in Risk & Control n°15.

- Fourth category: hazards linked to marine life

⚠ Risk n°19:

Being caught or tangled underwater due to algae fields

✓ Control n°19:

During the training organised in Belgium, some time will be spent to optimize the configuration of all divers' equipment to make sure that it comprises as little protruding elements as possible, thereby reducing the risk of entanglement. When performing underwater tasks, diver will be reminded to be aware of any sampling

gear, such as sampling bags or ropes from sediment cores, that could be caught by one element of the environment. To avoid any unnecessary risk, divers will be advised to keep out of algae fields when no work in those are needed. All divers will have to carry a line cutter (e.g., Eezycut) and a knife/scissors during their dives that will be in an easy-to-reach position for the diver (i.e. “safety triangle” on the chest). Thus, divers will be able to free themselves from any light entanglement, or, as dives will always be performed by teams of two, to free their buddy if he/she is not able to get rid of the element responsible of the entanglement by him(her)self. Besides, any entanglement in the algae present in Antarctica is quite unlikely. Indeed, many of the algae forests are made of members from the Desmarestiales group, which only form small bushes, and whose resistance to any force applied is quite moderate. Additionally, the fronds of the kelp species present in Antarctica, *Himantothallus grandifolius*, grow parallel to the seafloor and do not form vertical canopies such as in the typical *Macrocystis pyrifera* kelp forests. Altogether, these factors reduce greatly the risk of entanglement in Antarctic algae.

⚠ Risk n°20:

Contact to leopard seals or other mammals (see Muir, Barnes & Reid (2006) “Interaction between humans and leopard seals”, British Antarctic Survey and Rupp & Hancock (2017) “Antarctic Dive Guide”, United States Antarctic Program)

✓ Control n°20:

Contact with leopard seals should be maintained as minimal as possible if not completely avoided. Prior to the dive the appointed visual watch will take a 10 min round of observation to make sure that no leopard seal is visible in any direction around the boat. This visual watch will stay on the deck of the RV Australis looking out for leopard seals with binoculars throughout the diving operations. For RIB dives, people onboard will keep watching for possible presence of leopard seals while on the way to the dive site. If leopard seals show up close to the dive site at any moment prior to the start of diving operations, the dive is cancelled and another dive site is chosen or another activity is undertaken. In case a leopard seal shows-up when the divers are underwater, the dive is called. If the seal is spotted on the surface, during tethered dives, a specific pull call will be given to the divers which will signal the presence of a leopard seal. For open water dives from the RIB, divers will be recalled according to the procedures described in the “Standard procedures for diving operations” section (tethered or untethered dives). If the seal is spotted by the divers, they will start ascending, staying as close as possible from each other, and, in case of tethered dive, make sure that the line and tender does not get in the way. If a leopard seal approaches the divers in the water and shows inquisitive behaviour, they should face the seal, hold any available gear out in front of them as a barrier, and swim slowly toward the RIB. The divers will ascend safely (less than 10m per min) and stay close to each other. The safety stop (5 min at 5 m) can be avoided in this case.

- Fifth category: hazards linked to scientific equipment

⚠ Risk n°21:

Damage/loss of the equipment/samples during transportation from the lab to the RIB, during transit to the dive site and during work

✓ **Control n°21:**

There will always be several people available for transportation from storage location to RIB and to handle the scientific equipment upon return from the field, meaning that no member of the team will be overloaded with equipment, avoiding the subsequent risk to drop sensitive gear/sample or to mishandling any piece of equipment. During transit with the RIB, all equipment will be secured to the handrail of the embarkation with the help of carabineers/hooks. When handed to the divers, the sampling gear will be directly attached by the surface tender to the D-rings of the divers' equipment to avoid any drop, and inversely at the end of every dive. For sediment cores, they will be lowered by the surface tender close to the bottom in a rack along a working line, and they will be raised directly back to the ship at the end of the task. In this rack, all sediment cores will be secured with robust bungees in order to make sure that they don't fall of during the descent or the ascent.

If scientific equipment is deployed and left on the seafloor for a certain period of time (e.g., sediment trap), it will be moored and marked with a buoy to make sure that it is retrieved at the end of the expedition. Additionally, its position will be recorded with a GPS transmitter in case of damage or loss of the buoy marking the location, to allow for a search & recovery operation (see description of the process p 35).

⚠ **Risk n°22:**

Interference with Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) operations

✓ **Control n°22:**

As the ROV pilot will also be part of the main diving team, the occasions when a ROV will be in the water at the same time as the divers will be limited. When these tasks will overlap, most of the time, the ROV and the divers will work different areas of the sampling location (e.g., ROV deployed from the RV Australis and divers from the C4 RIB (and vice & versa), or ROV deployed from the C3 RIB and divers from the C4 RIB in different parts of the sampling location). However, in the rare instances when both tasks will have to be led simultaneously from the RV Australis, the Chief Scientist and the Dive Leader will ensure that the ROV and the divers are launched from two different sides of the ship, so that the divers cannot interfere with the ROV. During this type of dive, divers will be instructed to take care not to pass on the other side of the boat during work underwater, in order to avoid contact with the ROV or with the umbilical that links it to the surface. If despite all these precautions contact is made between the ROV and the divers, the danger for them will be minimal. Indeed, propellers from the ROV do not protrude from its structure (see Figure 8), and any entanglement in the umbilical can be dealt with according to parts of the procedure described in the context of Risk & Control n°15.

Figure 8. Picture of the BlueROV2 used during the TANGO expeditions for seafloor mapping.

10.3 Mandatory equipment list

In accordance with article 6 of the Royal Decree of 23/12/2003, each diver's employer must ensure that the following personal safety equipment is made available to him or her, and arrange for any missing equipment to be purchased.

- Onboard of RIB

- 1) Lifejackets for non-divers on the RIB.
- 2) Safety 15L tank with two regulators + safety line (at least 6m long) for its deployment.
- 3) Handheld echosounder.
- 4) Handheld GPS.
- 5) DAN oxygenotherapy kit with 5L oxygen bottle (200 bars).
- 6) VHF radio in communication to the vessel.
- 7) Life line (1.5 cm diameter, min 60m long) attached to a fixed point in the boat + carabineer to attach the tether to the BCD of the dive leader from each buddy system (in case of tethered diving).
- 8) Diver Recall Signal.
- 9) Snowboard mask UV filter polarised (for during RIB driving to dive location with stormy conditions) or sunglasses with UV filters and side protection (calm weather and sunny conditions) for all persons onboard.
- 10) 6L barrel with red screwing cap for keeping dry/safe gloves hoods and other clothing and tools.
- 11) Thermos for tea/water and a bottle of water (2L).
- 12) Warm gloves for on the surface while waiting.
- 13) Warm hood covering ears for on surface while waiting.
- 14) Hand warmer to prevent extreme hand cold for diver during transit after their dive.
- 15) Space blanket in case of signs of hypothermia.
- 16) Scarf or buffs to cover neck and mouth while waiting on the surface.

- Diving equipment

- 1) Dry suit (+ spare or repair parts such as inflator, purge valve, sleeves...).
- 2) Thermic undergarment (more than one layer advisable) and/or heating jacket.
- 3) Dry gloves (+ backup \geq 7mm semi-dry gloves/mittens and backup rubber glove).
- 4) Under gloves.
- 5) Hood (min 7 mm neoprene).
- 6) Mask + spare mask.
- 7) BCD (backplate + wing for single tank).
- 8) Fins.
- 9) Leads with belt and/or weight pockets.
- 10) Fully enclosed membrane I stages (2).
- 11) II stage regulators for cold waters (2).
- 12) Pressure gauge + connection HP hose.
- 13) Connection LP hose to jacket and dry suit.

- 14) One large orange SMB with a reel/spool (at least 30m) + one emergency yellow SMB already equipped on reel/spool (at least 30m) and ready to be deployed per diver in the water.
- 15) Line cutter and knife/scissors (x2).
- 16) Diving lamp (+ spare battery).
- 17) Compass.
- 18) Fins with easy strap to wear them onboard or RIB.
- 19) Whistle.
- 20) Diving computer + spare battery if applicable (+ 1 spare computer advised).
- 21) Underwater slate.
- 22) Stainless-steel carabineers (mousquetons), bolt snaps and double-enders to attach equipment to jacket.
- 23) 2mm thick gasket to secure and assemble sampling gears.
- 24) Sampling bags of various sizes in accordance with the task foreseen.
- 25) Spare kit for the diving team (exact content tbd).

The dive gear will be configured following Hogartian style:

-Right tank: First stage + primary regulator on long hose (2m) + direct sytem on wing (~45 cm).

-Left tank: First stage + back-up regulator on short hose (~56 cm) + SPG (~60cm) + drysuit inflator (50-60cm).

This standardized configuration will minimize hazards due to wrong manipulation of the equipment in case of regulator freezing for instance, and will enhance security for air donation or emergency issues.

BCDs will be harness and backplates minimizing weak plastic buckles and not streamlined configurations. Equipment will be clipped on inox D-Ring with double enders.

10.4 Emergency plan TANGO 2

- Generalities

> All Belgian scientific diving operations are carried out following rules of the Royal Decree 23/12/2003 including the introduction of the divers to the operational risk management document that they will sign before the beginning of the expedition.

> The safety-equipment in RIB is mentioned in section 10.3.

> Prior to every diving activity two briefings take place: one on the evening before the diving takes place (the general meeting) and one in the morning prior to the diving (the Diving meeting). Topics of the latter are the aim of the dive, the description of the scientific task, the planning of the dives (e.g. depth & estimated dive time) and the procedure before/during/after the dive in terms of mobility & safety.

> A visual watch from R/V Australis vessel will be assigned and put into place for the duration of the diving activities and the watch will be provided of a VHF radio. The skipper will always be available and reachable by radio as well on the same channel.

> At arrival on site the vessel and visual watch will be informed by radio to prove that the communication is working – a radio contact with the Australis and the visual watch will also take place in case of changing the dive site and each time the dive team has finished one task and the divers are out of the water. All ship crew have marine radio operator certificates for all marine channels. Squelch is set manually - just higher than / above feedback. Radio checks are often carried out before departing from Australis.

- **Medical emergency due to diving operations**

At the beginning of the expedition, the safety procedure will be reviewed between all members of the team.

1) Problem underwater (gear failure, air loss, ...)

Whatever the problem the divers encounter underwater (air loss, gear failure, scientific gear failure/loss, ...), they should shoot the yellow SMB to warn the surface security that something is wrong. As the yellow SMB pops out of the surface, the skipper of the RIB will directly navigate towards the divers and the deco-line with the spare tank and regulator will be clipped on the SMB line and deployed. In this case the divers will have enough air to make their safety stop and then surfacing. If there was any excessive speed during the ascent, the primary diver in charge of leading the dive will decide to extend the safety stop for a few minutes.

2) Buddy loss

If the two divers were diving untethered and lose each other, then each diver should look around them twice, check the water column above and below, and if there is no sight of the buddy, they should shoot their SMB and start their ascent. In this case, the surface security will see both SMB and directly know that the divers are separated. If they were diving at a maximum depth of 20 m, they should meet at the surface within 2 to 3 minutes. In this case, the safety stop of 5 min at 5 m is not made.

3) Problems related to the diver (decompression sickness or not) or decompression sickness suspicion

-Short of breath underwater

The divers should stop any task/scientific activities, warn his/her buddy, stop and knee on the bottom, and take the time to recover. If after a few breathing cycles the diver cannot recover, abort the dive. Air quality is controlled during the expedition to avoid such situations. Divers will take care to maintain a good physical state before and during the expedition as well.

-Injured diver still conscious

If a diver surface with an injury or any suspicion of decompression sickness (DCS); the mobile RIB will recover the divers onboard and directly bring them on the RV Australis where the injury could be healed depending on the gravity. If the injury does not allow the diver to move by himself, then the security diver may jump on the water and give some help. If there was an ascent with excessive speed, then as safety precaution the divers will take oxygen for 30 min at 15L/min. If there is any suspicion of DCS (dizziness, extreme fatigue, skin itching, joint pain, ...), the diver should take 100% oxygen with on-demand regulator first, as it provides the highest oxygen concentration and no oxygen waste, and then switch on the Wenoll Rebreather for longer treatment. The DAN emergency number (+39 0642115685) should be called and they will give instructions to follow.

Summary of barotrauma related to scuba-diving and methods to avoid them

They can occur when ascend speed is excessive, when there is no expiration during the ascent, when there is a shortness of breath, or in case of stress or panic with an uncontrolled ascend. In any case, ascending from depth should be done in a controlled speed, taking care to breath out properly. Barotraumas are:

Ears	Take care not forcing Valsalva manoeuvre, do not use cotton buds to clean ears
Sinuses	Do not dive if cold symptoms, nose clogged
Eyes	Expire with the nose in the mask when descending to the bottom
Teeth	Keep a good buccal hygiene
Colic	Abort dive
Lungs	The most serious barotrauma that can lead to death. Expire during ascent

A. Pneumothorax

Symptoms: chest pain, difficulty to breath, blue skin, blood froth in the mouth, faint

B. Pneumomediastinum

Symptoms: crepitation in the chest

C. Emboly

Symptoms: intense chest pain

-Injured diver unconscious

If a diver is surfacing with his/her buddy unconscious, then all the safety loop will be deployed with the retrieval of the unconscious diver by the RIB (with the help of the back-up diver or not) and then the basic life support will be given (CPR chain with oxygenotherapy) following the procedures learnt with DAN trainings.

In any case of emergency, the surface tender or the RIB driver inform the visual watch and the skipper on the RV Australis of the situation through VHF on dedicated channel. Simultaneously to the repatriation of the injured diver, the skipper will first evaluate all assets in the area and take contact with the nearest ships and station to warn that their assistance might be needed for an evacuation.

During the repatriation, the following procedure must take place:

A) Steps in the RIB during the way back to the vessel

Free the diver of the equipment including the tanks, the jacket, and the mask directly at the surface before moving him/her onboard. Keep the diver protected of the wind/snow/water and try to keep the diver awake if conscious. If the diver is responsive, rescuers should try to ask the diver or his/her buddy what happened and ask details on the symptoms he/she feels (to be then collected onto the appropriate incident sheet). If the symptoms suggest a decompression incident or a lung over-pressure injury, or if the diver is in a state of shock, administer normobar oxygen 100% at a constant flow of 15L/min with the oxygen bottle connected to the non-rebreather mask. If unconscious, get the vitals. If the unconscious diver is not breathing carry out CPR, assisted with the oxygen tank connected to a bag valve mask:

NB: If a drowning is suspected, start first with 5 insufflations before starting CPR.

1. Kneel next to the person and place the heel of your hand on the breastbone at the centre of their chest. Place the palm of your other hand on top of the hand that's on their chest and interlock your fingers.
2. Position yourself so your shoulders are directly above your hands.

3. Using your body weight (not just your arms), press straight down by 5 to 6cm on their chest.
4. Keeping your hands on their chest, release the compression and allow their chest to return to its original position.
5. Repeat 30 times these compressions at a rate of 100 to 120 times per minute
6. Administer two oxygen insufflations with the help of a manually triggered ventilator; don't insist if these insufflations don't go through.
7. Repeat this cycle of compressions/insufflations until back at the RV Australis.

B) Steps on the RV Australis

Once at the boat, transfer the diver inside to protect him/her from the weather and assess his/her status, based on the information available. If a decompression accident or a lung over-pressure injury is suspected, or if the diver is in a state of shock, continue the administration of normobar oxygen 100% at a constant flow of 15L/min. In the meantime, prepare the Wenoll Emergency Oxygen Rebreather, and switch to this unit as soon as possible to ensure proper oxygen treatment throughout the potential evacuation. If still unconscious, continue the CPR started on the RIB, and administer pure oxygen to the victim with a manually triggered ventilator. Depending on the seriousness of the incident, and/or if the diver does not feel better after 30 min administration of 100% oxygen at atmospheric pressure, the skipper will start the evacuation procedures.

>The closest hyperbaric chambers are at Rothera Station (Adelaide Island, at about 240 nautical miles distance from the planned sampling location of Foyn Harbour for example, for around 36h of navigation, Fig. 9) and at Carlini Station (King George Island, at about 170 nautical miles from the planned sampling location of Foyn Harbour, for around 24h of navigation, Fig. 9).

If the emergency is not related to diving *per se* or if it does not necessitate a recompression in a hyperbaric chamber, assess the seriousness of the injury, ideally in concertation with the MD in charge of the follow-up of the members of the expedition if he/she can be reached quickly, and decide with the skipper whether it can be treated onboard of the RV Australis or if an evacuation to a nearby facility is necessary.

> The closest medical facilities are given in Fig. 9: Vernadsky Station (Galindes Island, around 9 to 80 nautical miles depending on the sampling locations, corresponding to 1h30 to 11h30 of navigation), Palmer Station (Anvers Island, around 20 to 65 nautical miles depending on the sampling locations, corresponding to 3h to 9h30 of navigation), Melchior Station (Melchior Island, around 1 to 55 nautical miles depending on the sampling location, corresponding to < 1h to 8h of navigation at full speed) and Yelcho Station (Doumer Island, around 20 to 55 nautical miles depending on the sampling locations, corresponding to 3h to 8h of navigation).

Possible helicopter intervention request will be considered whenever close enough (50-100 nautical miles to allow a return flight in safety) to the medical facilities, especially if the use a hyperbaric facility is needed. This option will be decided by the skipper in concertation with the Rothera or Carlini Station authorities.

Figure 9. Antarctic bases with medical facilities. Hyperbaric chambers are available in Rothera and Carlini stations.

C) Follow-up procedures

During transfer to the medical facilities, the victim will stay in observation in a safe and comfortable place of the boat with at least one expedition member constantly at his/her side to ensure that his/her condition does not worsen. In the meantime, contact will be made with the insurer of the victim to coordinate a potential repatriation from Antarctica, and to arrange the necessary care that couldn't be provided on site. Additionally, the family of the victim will be warned as soon as possible from the incident, and will be kept updated about any significant development in the rescue effort or about any change in the patient status.

- Divers lost at sea

Divers will be declared lost following three cases:

- 1) During a tethered dive, if contact is lost with the divers for more than 10 minutes without any visible SMB at the surface.
- 2) During an untethered dive, if after 10 minutes past the maximum bottom time planned and after recalling the divers, no SMB is visible at the surface.
- 3) During any dive, if a diver surfaces without his/her buddy and he/she does not emerge 5 minutes after the surfacing of the first diver.

A) Action steps for the safety team

In case of lost divers, the surface tender and the RIB driver inform the visual watch and the skipper on the RV Australis that divers are missing. The visual watch will then immediately call the two remaining divers who will gear up. Meanwhile, the skipper and the Scientific Crew Leader will consult current charts (if available) to determine the potential direction of drift from the diver(s). Similarly, if one of the divers surfaced alone, the surface tender and the first RIB driver will question him/her regarding the presence of any current at the

bottom, and if present, about its direction. Once ready, the remaining divers will board the second RIB with a crew member and bring the necessary equipment to conduct a search & rescue operation (i.e., a weighted shotline with a buoy to mark the entry point of the lost divers and serve as starting point for the search, a GPS to position the shotline and a reel to perform a circular search, a compass to keep track of the search pattern). The details of the S&R operations are the following (also applicable for the loss of scientific equipment):

- 1) Deploy a weighted shotline attached to a light buoy above the GPS point corresponding to the sampling site explored, or, if only one diver is lost and his/her buddy has information about their progression during the dive away from the GPS entry point, a few meters away from the reference point in the direction advised by the buddy.
- 2) Deploy the team of two rescue divers close to the shotline.
- 3) Once ready, the two divers descend along the shotline and attach the reel 1m above the bottom to the line.
- 4) Depending on the visibility, the rescue leader (i.e., most experienced diver of the buddy system) extends the reel to a certain length (10m maximum) away from the shotline, depending on the visibility on site.
- 5) Once the optimal length is reached, the second diver position itself at mid-point between the first diver and the shotline origin, making sure that both are visible.
- 6) Once both in position, divers begin to swim in circle to perform a circular search pattern; the rescue leader keeps track with its compass of the progression from the circle.
- 7) Once a first circle is completed, if the lost diver was not found, the rescue leader extends further the reel to broaden the search pattern, and the second diver reposition itself along the reel line to assure coverage of the new search area; then an additional turn is performed.
- 8) Repeat the steps until the lost diver is found, or until usual dive limits are reached (i.e. 1/3 of the air reserve, 5 mins before no-deco limit, appearance of any feeling of coldness).

At the same time, if current information was available, the skipper and the Chief Scientist will guide one of the RIB in the right direction, and this first embarkation will start looking for divers adrift at the surface at a certain distance from the boat, while the other RIB stays around the divers performing the S&R operations close to the entry point, ready to assist them. If no clues on the direction of drift from the divers exist, the RIB will perform a search with a broad circular pattern around the ship, complementing the circular pattern performed underwater. On the RV Australis, the skipper will inform all ships and research stations in the vicinity of the missing diver and will coordinate potential assistance in the search for the missing divers.

B) Possible actions of the diver(s) lost at sea

Divers have to stay as calm as possible, and if lost together, buddies should stay as close as possible until the arrival of the rescuers. They should make use of their whistles. After inflation of the BCD to float effortlessly at the surface of the water, divers can discard any bulky sampling gear that would weight them down. Then, if not already done, SMBs are deployed and, if two SMBs are available, one is kept upright for any rescuers coming from the sea, and one is laid horizontally on the water, as in this position it can be easier to spot from the air. The SMB, can be used as a flotation device to be more stable at the surface of the water. In case of cooling, and if divers have any notion of the direction from which they have drifted, they can start to gently

fin in that direction. Exertion must be avoided, but a certain level of activity will help to delay hypothermia. If a ship/helicopter/aircraft is sighted, making large gestures and blow in an emergency whistle can help to attract its attention. In low light conditions, a lamp can be used to illuminate the SMB, or/and can be pointed directly towards any incoming rescuers to alert them.

Summary of the Decompression Sickness Procedures

50% appears in the first 30 min post-dive

99% within 6 hours

100% 12–24 hours

1) Minor symptoms

- Extreme or unusual fatigue after the dive
- Unusual dizziness after the dive
- Skin itching

➔ 30 to 60 min with 100% oxygen

2) Major symptoms

- Anxiety, stress, fatigue
- Sensitivity loss
- Paralysis
- Blotches on skin
- Deafness
- Giddiness
- Vomiting

➔ 100% oxygen – hydration – emergency plan deployed, and DAN called

3) Type of sickness, from least serious to death danger:

- A. Skin related: itch, blotch, swelling
- B. Osteo-articular: bends (shoulders, knees, elbows)
- C. Choke: DCS of the lung
- D. Internal ear: dizziness, giddiness, vomiting, visual troubles, deafness
- E. Neurological: Mono/hemiplegy, tetra/quadruplegy, not possible to speak anymore, coma, epilepsy, or medullary (spinal cord), difficulty to urinate, difficulty to move legs

11. Annexes

11.1 Sediment trap sketch

11.2 Summary of identified risks & control measure

Risk identified	Severity	Risk control	Severity after control
<i>Hazards linked to the usage of high-pressure gas and of diving equipment</i>			
Use of high-pressure compressor	High	Use by competent personnel & equipment fulfilling regulations	Low
Use of high-pressure diving tanks	Moderate	Follow Belgian legislation or local if more restrictive, all tanks have been purchased new prior to the start of the TANGO project	Low
Pollution of the breathing gas	Moderate	Follow EU 12021 norm, both generators will be serviced before the beginning of the cruise, additional use of personal filters	Low
Personal diving equipment loss or damage	Low to moderate	Specific insurances arranged by the employer to cover the cost of repair/replacement	Low
Faulty/malfunctioning equipment (dry suit, regulators, etc...)	Moderate to high	Starting with equipment in perfect condition and serviced prior to the cruise and tested prior to packing; taking care of diving equipment with daily rinsing and proper storage to avoid freezing; fixing if needed and hence the availability of spare parts and a complete backup sets	Low
<i>Hazards linked to boat and boat operation</i>			
Working in a slippery zone.	Moderate to high (rainy conditions)	Drainage of the floor, attention while moving around on the boat/RIB, defrosting of deck with salt	Low

Wrong handling of the boat, missing safety equipment, breakdown.	Low	The RIBs are operated by competent personnel and the safety equipment is regularly checked	Low
<i>Hazards linked to the diving operations</i>			
Strong currents that could make the dive difficult or the divers drifting	Moderate	Follow minimal current tidal window for diving; assessment of current strength upon arrival on a new site; tethered diving if current present	Low
Bad weather conditions such as fog or strong waves that may endanger the persons and/or the gear during transfer between the RIB and main vessel, or put divers at risk divers when going in and out of the water.	Moderate to high	No dives in foggy or windy conditions (H ₀ lower than 1 m and wind speed < 5knots)	Low
Third-party boats traffic (tourism, military or scientific) causing a collision with a diver.	Moderate	Work area outside the shipping routes; signalling of divers underwater; watch of incoming traffic and communication	Low
Poor visibility in the water due to particles influx linked to summer freshwater runoffs	Moderate	Training in low visibility conditions; tethered diving if very bad visibility; use of powerful lights	Low
Diving in polluted waters	Moderate	Diving in unsettled & nearly pristine areas; use of drysuits & drygloves	Low

Decompression sickness	High	No-decompression dives; sufficient rest and good hydration of divers; safety margin of 3 min before the no-decompression limit; careful monitoring of the NDL time (+ alarm); safety stop 5 min at 5 m after each dive; additional safety stop after unplanned mandatory decompression stop	Low
Freezing of a regulator	Moderate	Use of regulators adapted to cold-waters; appropriate set up and routing of equipment and hoses; maintenance of compressors; use of additional personal filters	Low
Out of air situation	Moderate to high	Teams of two divers; careful monitoring of air consumption; conservative air management; availability of safety tank	Low
Cooling/hypothermia of the divers	High	Do not dive if too cold before entering the water; hot drink available on the RV Australis and also on RIB; use of ad-hoc protective equipment during transit; use of drysuit and adequate thermic underwear; abort the dive if too cold	Low
Diving under brash ice, collision with drifting ice, wave due to collapsing iceberg or ice front	Moderate to high	No dives under fast-ice; tethered dives under brash ice; watch for drifting ice when sailing to the dive site & sail at moderate speed; stay at a safe distance of ice-cliff and large icebergs; call the dive/change dive site in case too much drifting ice is present; abort the dive if ice conditions worsen.	Low

Entanglement in the line during tethered dives or entanglement of the line in the environment	Moderate	Teams of two divers; training of divers to tethered dives; availability of cutting tools; removable attachment of tether to the diver	Low
<i>Hazards linked to marine life</i>			
Being caught or tangled underwater due to algae fields.	Low	Low probability of being tangled in Desmaretiales & <i>Himantothallus sp.</i> ; teams of two; optimisation of configurations; availability of cutting tools	Low
Contact to leopard seals or other mammals	Low to moderate	Pre-dive surveys to be done by visual watch; dive aborted in case of leopard seal present; continuous survey during dives; dive aborted in case of encounter underwater	Low
<i>Hazards linked to scientific equipment</i>			
Damage/loss of the equipment/samples during transportation from the lab to the RIB, during transit to the dive site and during work.	Moderate	Use equipment carefully; find a proper location within the RIB while working to avoid trampling on it; while on the water always secure the instruments to an attachment point; deploy into the water with the help from the boat	Low
Interference with Remotely Operated Vehicule (ROV) operations.	Moderate	Dissociation in time of diving and ROV operations; operations in separate areas of the sampling station; deploy from two different sides of the boat; teams of two divers; availability of cutting tools	Low

11.3 Detailed description of underwater tasks

- WP1:

A) Underwater photography of benthic organisms and collection of voucher specimens to build a genetic barcode library of organisms

During this dive, one diver will take care of the photography of the benthic species encountered with the help of a Olympus TG6 camera and a video light. Simultaneously, his/her assistant will take care of the collection from the target specimen. Collected individuals will be placed in a Trident self-closing collection bag, handled by the assistant who also monitors the diving parameters. As Dr. Camille Moreau is the most experienced underwater photograph, he will be the main performer of this task.

B) Collection of specimens from the sea urchin *Sterechinus neumayeri* and of its potential food sources (algae and sediments)

For this task, two divers will be equipped each with a Trident collection bag. The primary diver will search for the sea urchin ($n = 25$), while the assistant will swim alongside him/her and collect potential food sources of the animals, such as algae and superficial sediments. For the latter, he/she will use three Falcon tubes (50mL) prefilled with water to ensure their negative buoyancy, placed in the collection bag. When the required number of specimens is collected, or when other parameters impose the end of the dive, specimen are brought to the main ship for dissection.

- WP2:

A) Quantitative sampling of benthic fauna and flora

For each sampling station, this task requires two dives, split between two consecutive days. During each dive, the primary diver is equipped with either a 30 m weighted measure tape or a weighted PVC quadrat (40cm x 40cm), and with a putty knife to help detaching fixed organism and scrape the seafloor during quadrates. He/she is joined by the assistant diver who carries three Trident self-closing collection bag, each one of them containing a Falcon tube (50mL) prefilled with water to ensure its negative buoyancy. Once in the water, at the pre-agreed depth, the primary diver sets the quadrat or transect (10m) on the seafloor. In the meantime, if soft sediment is present, the assistant takes a superficial sediment sample.

For the transect, the assistant then gives an empty collection bag to the primary diver, who begins to swim alongside the transect and collects all mega-invertebrates (≥ 5 cm) encountered. After the end of this first transect, the primary diver exchanges its full bag for an empty one with the assistant diver and rolls back the measure tape. Then, both divers swim a few meters and repeat this sequence, for a total of three transects.

For the quadrat sampling, both divers kneel on opposite sides of the sampling unit. The assistant diver holds the collection bag open, while the primary diver uses the putty knife to scrape all organisms in the

surface, and transfer them into the open bag. In this process, the assistant diver makes sure than no organism is lost or manages to escape the collection bag. Then, as for transects, both divers swim a few meters away to lay another quadrat, and repeat the sequence, up to three sampling units.

After completion of the three sampling units, or after reaching any of the dive limits planned, divers make sure that all tools and sampling bags are securely attached to their BCD, and start their ascent.

B) Deployment of an ROV for the mapping of the seafloor and of the benthic communities targeted

Under normal circumstances, no divers should be involved in this task. However, if the ROV happened to be stuck underwater due to entanglement for example, with no rupture of the umbilical, divers will be sent to free it. In this situation, a team of two divers will board the RIB with a surface tender and a crew member to drive the zodiac, and go in the water above the location sent by the ROV to the piloting station, and follow the umbilical towards the ROV. They will then free the machine with the help of cutting tools if necessary, and as it is positively buoyant, let it ascent back to the surface if is not drown. As this machine is very light in the water, no lift bags should be needed. Once back at the surface, the ROV will be hauled in the RIB, and brought back to the RV Australis. Throughout this operation, the ROV pilot will stay at the piloting station and make sure that the ROV is in standby mode, with no risk to activate the propellers. If the ROV loses contact with the RV Australis through the rupture of the tether, divers will be sent to its last known location, and perform a Search & Recovery operation as detailed at page 35 to bring the machine back to the surface, then onto the RIB and back to the RV Australis.

- WP3

A) Sediment coring

For this task, two different types of cores will used, and so during separated dives. The first type of core, with a 5.6 cm diameter, will be used to collect the soft bottom infauna for stable isotopes analysis and to measure environmental variables (sediment grain size, pigments analysis, total organic matter, total organic carbon content and total nitrogen). For this purpose, once above the sampling point, a rack containing five corers (open) is lowered down to 1m above the seafloor, attached to a rope secured to the railing of the RIB. When the rack is in position, divers enter the water, and go down along the line to the seafloor. There, the two divers take successively the different corers and collect sediment cores around the position of the rack. To do so, the corers are inserted open in the sediment. Once fully inserted, the above cap is closed, and the corer full of sediment is gently extracted vertically from the sediment, taking care not to disturb the layering of the material. Once outside of the sediment matrix, the lower cap is gently inserted into the bottom of the corer, while slightly opening the above cap to let the overlying excess water escape to avoid overpressure in the corer, which would disturb the superficial part of the sediment core. When full, the divers place the corers back into the rack, secured with a bungee, and take another core to perform another extraction a few meters away. When all five sediment extractions are done, and that all cores are secured in the rack with bungees, the divers then ascend along the sediment rack rope and use it as visual reference to accomplish their safety

stop. Once the divers are at the surface, the sediment rack is then raised by the tender and brought back onto the RIB, with the help of the divers to stabilise it when transiting from the surface to the RIB.

The second type of core, with a 10 cm diameter, will be used for incubation of sediments to measure the primary productivity of the soft bottom benthic community, the nutrients dynamic and the gas exchanges between the sediment community and the water column. For this purpose, as for smaller cores, a rack containing nine large corers (open, secured with bungees) is lowered down to 1m above the seafloor, attached to a rope secured to the railing of the RIB. When the rack is in position, divers enter the water, and go down along the line to the seafloor. There, the primary diver gets in position, while the assistant fetches the large core and opens the top valve inserted into the top cap. Then, he/she passes the corer to the primary diver, who pushes vertically the corer into the sediment down to the deepest level possible. Then, the assistant gets ready next to the corer full of sediment with the lower cap. Once all in position, the primary diver closes the top valve and start to gently extract the corer from the sediment matrix. During this process, the assistant helps to stabilise the corer, in order to avoid any jerks that could disturb the sediment layering. Once outside of the sediment matrix, the assistant quickly inserts the lower cap into the bottom of the corer, while the primary diver slightly opens the above top valve to let the overlying excess water escape to avoid overpressure in the corer, which would disturb the superficial part of the sediment core. Once a core is completed, the primary diver gets in position some meters away from the previous extraction, and the assistant puts the full corer back into the rack and secures it with bungees, before bringing an empty corer to the primary diver. When all three sediment extractions are done, and that all cores are secured in the rack with bungees, the divers then ascend along the sediment rack rope and use it as visual reference to accomplish their safety stop. Once the divers are at the surface, the sediment rack is then raised by the tender and brought back onto the RIB, with the help of the divers to stabilise it when transiting from the surface to the RIB.

B) Retrieval of a sediment trap

This sediment trap is typically deployed upon arrival on a new sampling location, and left on the seafloor to collect suspended matter until the RV Australis moves to another sampling location. It is deployed with the help of the RV Australis winch (max capacity of 680 kg), and its exact GPS position is recorded upon deployment. When the time has come to retrieve the sediment trap, a team of two divers and a tender is brought above the GPS location of the unit, and a shotline is dropped on this point. Then divers go down along the shotline, equipped with a 50kg lift bag (managed by the assistant diver) and with the required gear (managed by the primary diver) to perform a circular search as describe in the Search & Rescue protocol page 35. Once at the bottom, they begin to search for the sediment trap following this protocol. Note that, during the TANGO 1 expedition, visibility was so good on each site and the GPS coordinates were so accurate, that divers immediately found the sediment trap once at the bottom, and didn't need to perform a proper circular search.

Once divers have found the sediment trap, the first thing is to retrieve the sample (small bottle). Then the primary diver will shoot the SMB to signal the exact location to the RIB, who will position itself close to the SMB at the surface. The SMB will be attached to the sediment trap itself, to make sure that its position cannot be lost. When the sediment trap is properly tagged, divers will detach the quick release shackle, to let the sediment trap ascend to the surface thanks to the associated rigid buoys. At this moment, it is critical that

both divers make sure to stay on the side of the sediment trap, and not above or below, so that they do not interfere with its ascend or are not in the way if a problem arises and the sediment trap sinks instead of going up. Once at the surface, the sediment trap and the associated buoys are retrieved by the tender and the RIB driver, taking care to maintain it as vertical as possible to avoid spilling or damaging the cups containing the suspended matter. After this first step, the assistant diver will give the primary diver the 50kg lift bag, who will attach it to the anchoring point on the 40kg weight that used to stabilise the sediment trap. Therefore, he will use a stainless-steel D-shackle (safe working load > 1t), further secured with a metallic wire to ensure that the screw pin of the shackle cannot escape its thread. Once securely in place, the assistant diver will check that the weight cannot get entangled in features of the seafloor, and when it is signalled clear, the primary diver will start to gently inflate the lift bag, and start ascending with it while continuously controlling its speed. This inflation must be extremely progressive and the diver must avoid any prolonged outburst of air. Indeed, in these cold conditions, such solicitation of the regulators is bound to cause freezing and free-flow, even with cold-resistant regulators. Therefore, the assistant diver must be close to the primary diver, ready to close its valve if necessary. During the ascent, both divers have to stay next to the weight and the lift bag, not above or below, and have to control the stability of the assemblage, making sure it doesn't sway exaggeratedly. Once at the surface, the coupling weight/lift bag is secured to the RIB with a nylon rope, and the divers get out of the water as explained in the general procedure. When all divers are out of the water, the tender or the driver signals the RV Australis that they can approach the RIB. The main vessel position itself at close proximity to the RIB, who manoeuvres slightly to position the coupling weight/lift bag in reach of the RV Australis winch. Then, the iron weight is securely attached to the winch cable, and is brought back onto the RV Australis.

END OF THE WORKING STATEMENT METHOD